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NEW THERMOSET MATRIX BASED ON BISOXAZOLINES

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Thermoset Applications and Properties

Renewable energy

coatings/piping

Lightweight

Epoxy-Based Materials

Disadvantages:

- Brittleness (low flexibility)
- Temperature resistance
- low flame retardancy
- Low smoke/ toxicity properties

waterfront building site in Sydney's CBD, 2018

Untapped potential

Calidur = Bisoxazoline + Epoxy

Thermal and Fire behaviour

Fig1. Thermo-mechanical properties of composite materials was determined by DMA.

Fig2. TGA comparison curve for cured resin, in Nitrogen.

Conclusion:

- ✓ BOX resins with long shelf life, very high glass transition temperature, excellent thermal stability, and Fire retardancy will be suitable to use in engine, Oil and gas applications.
- ✓ glass transition temperature (Tg) is significantly high (~over 150°C) and the decomposition temperature is around 400°C.
- ✓ High char yield > 42% and improvement in flexural modulus and strength and for modified resin system.
- ✓ By modifying the Calidur system with high thermal stable resin system such as benzoxazine, Araldite®, and polyethersulfone the mechanical, thermal and fire properties are significantly improved.